

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DIFFERENT TEACHING METHODS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Introduction

This study examines the success rates of numerous methods of teaching English. It will discuss how different types of methods help improve certain skills in students. These techniques have changed over time, and the addition of technology has further modified education and how teachers could implement their methods in only teaching. The review will examine studies on several methods, including more modern Communicative Language Teaching, Task-Based learning, and Project - based Learning. In the modern era of technology, teachers aim to determine the best approaches for encouraging successful English language acquisition by analyzing the advantages and disadvantages of each method.

Identifying the different teaching styles.

According to Khattak and Usman (2011), the questionnaires aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of the course content, class activities, and teaching methods adopted in these language institutes. The result of questionnaires among 76 students from different language institutes showed that only 44.8% of students improved their speaking and listening skills after joining the institute. But 20.6% of them did not feel happy, as they said their experience of language learning at institutes did not bring any improvement in their speaking and listening skills. This means that most of the students did not improve their speaking and listening skills at these institutes. However, Sheikh and Mahmood (2014) evaluated the dominant teaching styles of the English language teachers and the effect of the distinct teaching styles on the motivation level of English language students. The data collection and questionnaires illustrated several teaching methods that teachers can use to help students learn better. For instance, the student-centered "Delegator" technique was most common among English language learners. The next two most common approaches were teacher-centered "expert" and "role model." The results reflect that the most

prevalent style among English language learners was "Delegator," which is student-centered. The next two prevalent styles were "Expert" and "Role Model", which are teacher-centered. Moving forward, Schmidt and Watanabe (2014) commented on their work as "those who notice most, learn most" and mentioned that "no noticing, no acquisition". Moreover, Schmidt and Watanabe reviewed research on noticing in order to understand the role of noticing in language acquisition. The result of this research proved that noticing may considerably affect the extent of learning, implicit learning is also a reality. The way children acquire L2 by interacting with peers and without explicit instruction brings forth the fact that implicit learning is possible as well as effective. However, regardless of its limitations, the noticing hypothesis has been the cause of significant theoretical and empirical research in language acquisition, providing an opening for integrating cognitive psychology into the theories of SLA. Moving forward, another study to understand the impact that task-based learning has on English language acquisition was conducted by Brown (2016). Additionally, the research teacher divided the class, which consists of 60 students, into two parts to understand the effectiveness of the lesson with task-based learning. The researcher was the main teacher in the two classes. The researcher carefully prepared the lessons for these two classes as well as collected periodical data. As a result, task-based language learning has been proven to be effective in improving comprehension and speaking fluency in English. At the same time, it is worth mentioning that Smith (2021) conducted research where he compared the analysis of teaching methods and identified that communicative language teaching showed the highest improvement in speaking and listening skills in student results. Moreover, when the focus is on communication, students are allowed to experiment with the language (L2) and, in turn, learn the language automatically. The focus is on identifying learners' communicative needs and classroom activities. In addition, this means that communication is the key element of student improvement in speaking and listening. However, Garcia (2018) used experimentation and control group comparisons to prove that project-based learning facilitated better retention and application of English language skills. The result of the experiment showed that the most recognized benefit of implementing a project in the foreign language classroom is improved language skills. Because students engage in purposeful communication to complete authentic activities, they have the opportunity to use language in a relatively natural context and participate in meaningful activities that require practical language use. Authentic activities

refer to activities designed to develop students' thinking and problem-solving skills, which are important in out-of-school contexts, and to foster learning. On the other hand, Patel (2017) did research and illustrated that direct grammar improved grammatical accuracy and writing proficiency. In addition, they had a longitudinal study and proficiency assessment, and the results showed that grammar instruction may be more effective at lower levels of proficiency. At higher levels, learners appear to process grammatical features more efficiently if they are self-directed. Learners in EFL contexts may require more grammar instruction to process limited input within their environment.

The use of technology impacts English language learning outcomes.

Moreover, some researchers emphasize that over time, technology became modern, and teachers started to use different technologies in teaching and, at the same time, continued to use their methods while conducting online classes. According to Nguyen (2015), they conducted research where they compared the analysis of traditional and online methods, and the results clearly showed that online teaching methods demonstrated equally effective results in English language learning. The study involved 19 students in an experimental group (online section) and 25 students in a control group (traditional section). Specifically, at the end of the course, online students seemed to have a higher preference for peer interaction, competition, interaction with the instructor, details of the course materials, independence, authority, reading, direct experiences, and clear goal setting. Moreover, there were no significant statistical differences detected in learning performance between both groups. Hence, Johnson (2020) also agreed with this statement and conducted a survey and observational study where he proved that technology integration positively correlated with improved reading and writing skills. This study underscores the vital educational potential and numerous benefits of technology in the language classroom for positive learning outcomes, and one of the ultimate goals of using modern technology is to actively engage students in language learning and motivate them to acquire it. During the observation of online classes, Johnson noticed ways in which students could gain feedback and improve their written communication and were engaged to write because of the technologies that they used. In addition, reading texts through their gadgets gave them the desire to engage in their task. Moreover, Ushioda (2020) had an experimental study using TILL and traditional classroom instruction. As a result, the TILL group showed greater improvement in all four skills compared to the traditional group, highlighting the potential of technology for enhancing language learning.

Current studies revealed that, if integrated skills teaching is implemented well, it is not only effective in improving students' language skills or language components but also supports the students and teachers as well. However, to run an English program employing the integrated language skills teaching approach, the teachers must have both competence and the belief that the approach can work effectively. Compared to teaching using the traditional segregated approach, the integrated skills approach requires a good understanding of discourse, the skills to use textbooks flexibly, and the readiness to implement the student-centered learning approach.

Conclusion

To summarize, the results of this review demonstrate how difficult it is to identify a single "best" method for learning English. The results show that teachers can implement different teaching methods in traditional classes as well as online. Hence, it emphasizes how important it is to choose and improve ways while keeping in mind learner needs, learning objectives, and context. Additionally, it highlights how various strategies and technology integration can be applied to create an engaging and effective learning environment for students with a range of backgrounds.

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